

Complexes of Uranium(IV) and Thorium(IV) with 1-Hydroxy-2-naphthoic Acid and 3-Hydroxy-2-naphthoic Acid

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Chelates of U(IV) and Th(IV) of the type, $U(OAc)_2L_2$, $U(OAc)_2L'$, $Th(OAc)_2L_2$ and $Th(OAc)_2L'$ (LH=1-OH-2-naphthoic acid and L'H=3-OH-2-naphthoic acid) have been synthesised from uranium and thorium tetraacetates in ethanol. Magnetic susceptibility, IR and electronic spectral data of U(IV) chelates and IR of Th(IV) chelates have been reported.

DESHPANDE and Rao¹ have synthesised and characterised the complexes of some lanthanons with the title ligands. Under present investigations chelates of U(IV) and Th(IV) with these ligands have been prepared and characterised on the basis of IR, electronic and magnetic susceptibility data.

Experimental

U(IV) and Th(IV) acetates were prepared as reported in literature^{2,3}. 1-OH-2-naphthoic acid (Kochlight) and 3-OH-2-naphthoic acid (Kochlight) were used without further purification. Ethanol was purified and dried by usual method.

Diacetatobis (1-hydroxy-2-naphthoato) uranium (IV) (Chelate-I): U(IV) acetate (0.50 g.) and 1-OH-2-naphthoic acid (0.40 g.) were mixed in ethanol (30 ml). Light green coloured complex got precipitated, after refluxing the contents for 4 hr. It was filtered, washed with ethanol and dried in *vacuo*. (Found : U, 33.00 per cent. Calcd : U, 32.60 per cent).

Diacetatobis (1-hydroxy-2-naphthoato) thorium (IV) (Chelate-II): 1-OH-2-naphthoic acid (1.13 g.) and thorium (IV) acetate (0.70 g.) were mixed in ethanol (25 ml). On refluxing for 4 hr. light brown coloured complex separated out, which was filtered, washed with ethanol and dried in vacuum. (Found : Th, 31.91 per cent. Calcd : Th, 32.04 per cent).

Triacetato (3-hydroxy-2-naphthoato) uranium (IV) (Chelate-III): 3-OH-2-naphthoic acid (1.57 g.) was mixed with U(IV) acetate (1.0 g.) in ethanol (25 ml). On refluxing for 1 hr. light brown coloured complex separated out which was washed with ethanol and vacuum dried. (Found : U, 39.46 per cent. Calcd : U, 39.54 per cent).

Diacetatobis (3-hydroxy-2-naphthoato) thorium (IV) (Chelate-IV): Th(IV) acetate (0.50 g.) was added to 3-OH-naphthoic acid (0.80 g.) in ethanol (20 ml). The contents were refluxed for 1 hr. when light yellow

coloured complex separated out which was washed with ethanol and dried in *vacuo*. (Found : Th, 31.84 per cent. Calcd : Th, 32.04 per cent).

Uranium and thorium were estimated as reported in literature⁴. IR spectra (nujol) of U(IV) and Th(IV) complexes were recorded in Specord-71 IR Spectrophotometer. Diffuse reflectance spectra of U(IV) chelates were recorded as reported in literature⁵. Magnetic susceptibilities of U(IV) chelates were measured at room temperature on Gouy balance.

Results and Discussion

The chelates are stable at room temperature and do not melt but decompose at higher temperatures giving U_3O_8 and ThO_2 at $\sim 650^\circ$ and $\sim 850^\circ$ respectively. They are insoluble in common organic solvents.

Hansberger⁶ and Desphande *et al.*¹ observed that in the IR spectra of 1-OH-2-naphthoic acid there was strong hydrogen bonding and -OH stretching frequency was absent whereas in 3-OH-2-naphthoic acid -OH stretching frequency was located at $\sim 3290\text{ cm}^{-1}$ probably due to weak hydrogen bonding. In the complexes of 3-OH-2-naphthoic acid the band was still present in the -OH stretching frequency region whereas in the complexes of 1-OH-2-naphthoic acid a distinct band was located in the -OH stretching frequency region¹.

IR spectra of the chelates of 1-OH-2-naphthoic acid with Th(IV) acetate and U(IV) acetate record a distinct band in the -OH stretching frequency region indicating that the ligand is not hydrogen bonded in the complexes (Table-1). In the chelates of 3-OH-2-naphthoic acid with Th(IV) acetate and U(IV) acetate the band is also present in the -OH stretching frequency region.

TABLE 1—INFRARED SPECTRAL DATA OF 1-OH-2-NAPHTHOIC ACID AND 3-OH-2-NAPHTHOIC ACID ALONG WITH THEIR COMPLEXES WITH ACETATES OF THORIUM (IV) AND URANIUM (IV) (IN CM⁻¹).

1-OH-2-naphthoic acid	Th(OAc) ₂ L [*] ₂	U(OAc) ₂ L [*] ₂	Probable assignment
—	3400–3100b	3400–3100b	—OH stretch
1650	1625s	1620s	C=O stretch
1575	1575vs } 1550sh } 1495w }	1570w	$\nu_{\text{asym}}(\text{OCO})$
	1410s	1405s	$\nu_{\text{sym}}(\text{OCO})$
3-OH-2-naphthoic acid	Th(OAc) ₂ L [*] ₂	U(OAc) ₂ L [*] ₂	Probable assignment
3200–3125	3325–3125b	3350–3150b	—OH stretch
1655 } 1620 }	1640s } 1610w }	1635s	C=O stretch
1595	1575sb } 1550sh } 1520sh }	1560sh } 1545sh } 1505s }	$\nu_{\text{asym}}(\text{OCO})$
	1340s	1340s	$\nu_{\text{sym}}(\text{OCO})$

LH^{*} = 1-OH-2-naphthoic acid and L^{*}H^{*} = 3-OH-2-naphthoic acid.
s=strong, vs=very strong, w=weak, b=broad, sh=shoulder, sb=strong broad.

In all these chelates the bands located in the ligand in C=O region appear with a slight downward shift indicating coordination from carbonyl oxygen. However, there seems to be overlapping for the $\nu_{\text{asym}}(\text{OCO})$ and $\nu_{\text{sym}}(\text{OCO})$ frequencies of the ligand and the acetate group.

Reflectance spectra of the chelates (I) and (III) (Table-2) are similar to the spectra of U(IV) complexes where uranium is eight coordinated^{4,5,7}.

The μ_{eff} of the chelates (I) and (III) are 2.74 and 2.88 B. M. which are comparable to that reported where U(IV) is eight coordinated^{4,5,7}.

TABLE 2—"STRONG" INTENSITY REFLECTANCE SPECTRA OF U(IV) COMPLEXES (IN NM)

Term ^a	Diacetato bis (1-OH-2-naphthoato) uranium(IV)	Triacetato (3-OH-2-naphthoato) uranium(IV)
³ F ₂	1940sh	1925sh
³ H ₅	1495s	1520s
³ F ₄	1300sh } 1190vs }	1150vs
³ F ₄	1060s	1050s
³ H ₆	1000sh } 840s }	900sh } 850s }
³ P ₀ , ¹ G ₄	665s } 645s }	650s
¹ D ₂	620m	620sh } 600s }
³ P ₁	550sh	555s
¹ I ₄	485s	480sh
³ P ₂	435m	440s

^a=assignments as given in reference 7.
s=strong, vs=very strong, m=medium, sh=shoulder.

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